

HIST 387:

New York City and the American Urban Experience

Dr. Adam Arenson

Spring 2016

MR 3:00-4:15pm (DLS 214)

Office Hours: MWR 12:15-1:45pm and by appt.

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*** READ THIS SYLLABUS CAREFULLY.**

*** THE INSTRUCTOR RESERVES THE RIGHT TO ALTER THIS SYLLABUS IF NECESSARY.**

Course Description

This course examines the history of New York City from its Lenape origins until yesterday, in the context of other cities in the United States and their development. Topics covered include the colonial and Revolutionary city, urban imperialism, the city in the American mind, immigration, social mobility, the rise of the ghetto, the impact of the New Deal, suburbanization, the modern metropolis, and recent trends.

Learning Objectives

At the completion of this course, students will show improvement in:

- Effective communication - oral and written, including:
 - Analyzing, evaluating, and synthesizing information and arguments and making sound judgments about their use and application.
 - Locating relevant information in printed and electronic form and credit it properly.
- Critical thinking
- Information and Technological Literacy
- Understand, interpret, and apply numerical data
- Independent and collaborative work, including functioning as independent thinkers and as members of collaborative groups.
- Global awareness - Understand and appreciate cultural diversity.
- Demonstration of a fundamental knowledge of historical causality and key events
- Ability to locate and integrate information from primary and secondary sources

Required Books (2 plus):

Our books are a collection of primary sources about New York City, and a new textbook framing U.S. urban history generally. As a class, we will create a narrative of New York City history, and discuss how it relates to national patterns. ***Always bring to class the texts assigned to be discussed that day, or partner with another in class to share them.***

1) Kenneth T. Jackson and David S. Dunbar, eds., *Empire City: New York through the Centuries* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2002). (\$18 or less used)

2) Lisa Krissoff Boehm and Steven H. Corey, *America's Urban History* (New York: Routledge, 2015). (\$50 or less used)

3) Additional articles and chapters as provided, and a MetroCard for library and site visits.

Course Methods

Most people misunderstand what history is, and what historians do. Historians tell stories about the past, but they also make an argument about the causes, course, and consequences of the events they describe. They investigate changes over time, analyze trends and patterns, and seek to make connections between the past and present. Historians may try to be objective, but they wrap their work in their beliefs. In this class, you will do historical work, and to read both primary sources and existing histories critically. Through repeating patterns of inquiry, students will have the chance to practice and improve their study strategies and writing ability. These skills are applicable to classes throughout your College career.

Statement on Technology in the Classroom

Our world is being transformed by a digital revolution, and computers and smartphones offer unprecedented power for research, connectivity, and connection. However, they also offer far too many distractions. In line with the latest education research (see for example <https://medium.com/@cshirky/why-i-just-asked-my-students-to-put-their-laptops-away-7f5f7c50f368> and <http://www.scientificamerican.com/article/a-learning-secret-don-t-take-notes-with-a-laptop/>), laptops and/or other digital equipment may not be used in this class unless you have made special arrangements with the professor. While we may, as a class, utilize our devices in some sessions, **in general all phones, laptops, etc. must be placed inside backpacks and out of view during class.**

Assignments

Forum Posts and Class Participation

200 points

Your participation grade has three factors. Beyond attendance, there are these:

Each class session, students should come to class prepared to discuss the readings, having thought about the course methods described above.

Each of the 18 readings-driven class sessions, students should post a question or comment about ONE of the week's readings ***before class*** to the Moodle site forum. The question or comment should be 100 to 300 words in length, and cover as many levels of significance as possible; postings will be graded on an 8-point scale, matching the centrifuges discussed on the first day. ***Only three students can post on a source per forum***; after that, discussion online must focus on other sources assigned.

Discussion Leading

300 points

Once during the semester, each student will lead class discussion. That week, the students' Moodle post can preview the themes they want to focus on, ***at least 24 hours before class***. Leaders should plan on directing the discussion for 60 out of the 75 minutes, asking questions that consider all of the readings for the day and the relationships between them. They should plan to draw out analyses from their fellow students, and direct discussion, not relying on the professor to do more than take group notes on the board and to keep track of pending speakers.

Assignments (cont.)

Semester-Long Research	200 points
Components:	
Regular Contributions to Online Databases	75 points
Black Quotidian Assignment	25 points
Self-Evaluation Reports	50 points
Presentation to the Class	50 points

Throughout the semester, students will track how the history of New York City play out on a single block, as well as tracking certain themes and keywords of interest through digitally searchable sources, and through a visit to their block. Students will compile their research in an online database and share their progress with the instructor and the class. (With luck, this research can serve as the basis of their final papers.) Further explanation and instruction will be provided in class.

Final Paper	300 points
Components:	
Ideas for Final Paper	25 points
Proposal for Final Paper, including Annotated Bibliography	50 points
Final Paper Outline	0 points
Final Paper Draft	0 points
Final Paper Presentation	0 points
Comments on Peer Drafts	25 points
Final Paper	200 points

All of the assignments are designed to help you conceive of, research, draft, revise, and perfect a paper about the history of New York City or U.S. urban history. The final paper will be 12-15 pages in length.

TOTAL	1000 points
A 940-1000 A- 900-939 B+ 880-899 B 840-879 B- 800-839	
C+ 780-799 C 740-779 C- 700-739 D+ 680-699 D 640-679 F Below 640	

All assignments should be turned in online, at the course Moodle site, on the date and at the time due. Late is better than never, but there will be a penalty, a full letter grade per week. If you find you need more time to complete the work, consult with the instructor **before** the assignment is due to avoid more points off.

Tardiness and Missing Classes

College policy dictates that **all** students attend **all** scheduled classes. Quizzes will often begin our classes; they cannot be made up, and any absences will hurt your participation grade. Please show respect to your peers and to our learning environment by arriving to class on time and remaining engaged for the entire scheduled time. Lateness and leaving the classroom before the end of class (even if you return) will be considered absences. If you miss four classes, you will be reported to the Dean's office.

Cheating, Plagiarism, Scholastic Dishonesty, and Student Discipline

All typewritten assignments will be submitted to Turnitin, an international plagiarism-detection database, via your Moodle submission. Students who engage in academic dishonesty will be subject to disciplinary action as stated in the College's Academic Integrity policy:

<https://manhattan.edu/community-standards-and-student-code-conduct - 32.Academic Integrity>

You must cite, reference, or quote information obtained from other sources so you give credit where credit is due.

Please use Chicago Style footnotes throughout. There is a guide at http://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org/tools_citationguide.html - use numbered examples. Do NOT copy any material regardless of where you obtained it into your own work. Do NOT submit work under your name if you did not complete it entirely yourself. In accordance with College policy, we will report instances of plagiarism and dishonesty to the Dean's office.

If you have questions about understanding and preventing plagiarism, please contact your instructor or the Manhattan College Writing Center <http://www.manhattan.edu/services/writing-center/>

Title IX and Non-Discrimination Notice

Manhattan College is committed to ensuring equal access to its educational programs and employment opportunities without regard to sex, gender, race, color, national origin, religion, age, disability, pregnancy, gender identity, sexual orientation, predisposing genetic characteristics, marital status, veteran status, military status, domestic violence victim status, or ex-offender status. The College will not tolerate harassing, violent, intimidating or discriminatory conduct by its students, employees or any other member of or visitor to the College community, which includes, without limitation, sexual harassment, sexual assault, domestic violence, dating violence, and stalking.

The College encourages individuals to report all gender-based misconduct immediately to the Title IX coordinator, one of the deputy coordinators or another College staff member. The College will fully and promptly investigate all allegations of gender-based misconduct and will impose disciplinary measures, or take similar actions, as may be appropriate. Title IX and the College strictly prohibits retaliation.

It is estimated that 20-25% of college women and 6% of college men will be the victims of sexual assault during their college careers. If you or someone you know has experienced sex- or gender-based violence or harassment, here are some important resources. You can use any or all of these resources, at your discretion. Contact campus Title IX Coordinator: Vicki Cowan, Mem 305, 718.862.7392, vicki.cowan@manhattan.edu or others listed here:

<https://manhattan.edu/about/human-resources/title-ix/who-to-contact-on-campus>

Learn more via Not Alone <https://www.notalone.gov/> EROC: End Rape On Campus (<http://endrapeoncampus.org>) and others.

Accessibility

Manhattan College seeks to provide reasonable accommodations for all qualified individuals with disabilities, including learning disabilities. This College will adhere to all applicable federal, state, and local laws, regulations and guidelines with respect to providing reasonable accommodations as required affording equal educational opportunity. It is the student's responsibility to register with Specialized Resource Center in Miguel 301B <http://manhattan.edu/academics/specialized-resource-center> within the first two weeks of classes, and inform the faculty member to arrange for appropriate accommodations.

Schedule of Meetings

Week 1	Jan. 25	<p>Introductions Course Outline Explaining Writing and Research Assignments: Weekly Responses, Discussion, Summary Paper, Block and Keyword Research, Research Paper Reading Strategies Historical Research and Writing: Sources, Context, Significance, Qualifications Read as soon as you can: <i>Empire City</i>, Introduction; <i>America's Urban</i>, Introduction.</p>
	Jan. 28	<p>New-York Historical Society History in Objects Workshop Sam Roberts, <i>A History of New York in 101 Objects</i> (New York: Simon & Schuster, 2014), Introduction, xvi-xx. DUE SUNDAY: Initial Ideas for Block Research and Keyword Research</p>
Week 2	Feb. 1	<p>New York's Original Inhabitants <i>America's Urban</i>, Chapter 1; Eric W. Sanderson, <i>Mannahatta: A Natural History of New York City</i> (New York: Abrams, 2009), Chapter 4, pp. 103-135.</p>
	Feb. 4	<p>New Amsterdam, Slavery, and Continental Europe's American Cities <i>Empire City</i> pp. 15-37; <i>America's Urban</i>, Chapter 2; Leslie M. Harris, <i>In the Shadow of Slavery: African Americans in New York City, 1626-1863</i> (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2004), Chapter 1, pp. 11-47.</p>
Week 3	Feb. 8	<p>Sources and Tips on NYC History Read: http://blackquotidian.com/anvc/black-quotidian/introduction and http://blackquotidian.com/anvc/black-quotidian/invitation-to-contribute Library Stacks, Scholarly Websites, and Tracking Platforms Our Online Database Digital Collaboration and You – starting with Black Quotidian</p>
	Feb. 11	<p>Colonial New York and Britain's American Cities <i>Empire City</i> pp. 38-80; <i>America's Urban</i>, Chapter 3 (first part). DUE: Black Quotidian assignment.</p>

Week 4	Feb. 15	Alexander Hamilton's City: American Revolution, American Capital <i>Empire City</i> pp. 81-98; <i>America's Urban</i> , Chapter 3 (finish); and <i>Hamilton</i> musical New York City songs, tracks #1, 5, 6, 8, 14, 23, 41, and 46 (purchase, score tickets, Spotify, or just lyrics analysis at http://genius.com/albums/Lin-manuel-miranda/Hamilton-original-broadway-cast-recording).
	Feb. 18	DUE: Up-to-Date Block Surveys, Keyword Searches, and Self-Reflections FIELD TRIP: Morris-Jumel Mansion Meet to take subway to 168 St.
Week 5	Feb. 22	Feeding the Metropolis: Republicanism, American Cities, and Hinterlands <i>Empire City</i> pp. 99-144; <i>America's Urban</i> , Chapter 4
	Feb. 25	New York and the World: Growth and Reform <i>Empire City</i> pp. 145-201; <i>America's Urban</i> , Chapter 5 (first part); John Kuo Wei Tchen, <i>New York Before Chinatown: Orientalism and the Shaping of American Culture, 1776-1882</i> (Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1999), Chapter 6, pp. 131-153.
Week 6	Feb. 29	New York and Freedom: Antebellum American Cities and a Nation Dividing <i>Empire City</i> pp. 202-254; <i>America's Urban</i> , Chapter 5 (part); and Timothy J. Gilfoyle, <i>City of Eros: New York City, Prostitution, and the Commercialization of Sex, 1790-1920</i> (New York: Norton, 1992), Chapter 6, pp. 119-142.
	Mar. 3	Civil War New York <i>Empire City</i> pp. 255-272; Edward K. Spann, <i>Gotham at War: New York City, 1860-1865</i> (Wilmington, Del.: Scholarly Resources, 2002), Chapter 8, pp. 93-105. DUE: Ideas for Final Paper
Week 7	Mar. 7	Gilded Age New York: The Birth of a Nation <i>Empire City</i> pp. 273-396. DUE: Proposal for Final Paper, including Annotated Bibliography
	Mar. 10	Reforming the American Cities and Progressive-Era New York <i>Empire City</i> pp. 397-518; <i>America's Urban</i> , Chapter 5 (finish).
Week 8		SPRING BREAK MARCH 14-18 – NO CLASSES
Week 9	Mar. 21	New York in World War: The Great Migration and Harlem Renaissance <i>Empire City</i> pp. 519-591; <i>America's Urban</i> , Chapter 6.

Week 9 (cont.)	Mar. 24	<p>Depression-Era New York and the New Deal in American Cities <i>Empire City</i> pp. 592-665; <i>America's Urban</i>, Chapter 7.</p> <p>FRI-MON EASTER BREAK</p>
Week 10	Tuesday Mar. 29	<p>DUE MONDAY NIGHT: Up-to-Date Block Surveys, Keyword Searches, Self-Reflections, and Final Paper Outlines From Sources to Outlines, from Outlines to Drafts Significance and Outside Perspectives</p>
	Mar. 31	<p>World War II and Postwar "Urban Renewal" and the Suburbs <i>Empire City</i> pp. 666-738; <i>America's Urban</i>, Chapter 8.</p>
Week 11	Apr. 4	<p>The 1960s: Civil Rights and the Response <i>Empire City</i> pp. 739-814; <i>America's Urban</i>, Chapter 9.</p>
	Apr. 7	<p>FIELD TRIP: Queens Museum Bring magnifying glasses/strong lens on camera if you can Read before you go: Zoe Rosenberg, "Unlocking the Secrets of New York City's Most Famous Model," <i>Curbed NY</i> February 27, 2015, http://ny.curbed.com/archives/2015/02/27/unlocking_the_secrets_of_new_york_citys_most_famous_model.php WE WILL NOT BE BACK BY 4:15</p>
Week 12	Apr. 11	<p>The 1970s: "New York, Drop Dead" <i>Empire City</i> pp. 815-839; <i>America's Urban</i>, Chapter 10 (first part); <i>Once Upon A Time In New York: The Birth Of Hip Hop, Disco & Punk</i> (BBC documentary, 2011, available online).</p>
	Apr. 14	<p>The 1980s: Greed is Good? <i>Empire City</i> pp. 840-890; <i>America's Urban</i>, Chapter 10 (finish); and Chapter 1 - "Class Struggle on Avenue B": The Lower East Side as Wild, Wild West" in Neil Smith, <i>The New Urban Frontier: Gentrification and the Revanchist City</i> (New York: Routledge, 1996), Chapter 1, pp. 3-29.</p>
Week 13	Apr. 18	<p>Presentation of your Research Work on your Paper</p>
	Apr. 21	<p>Presentation of your Research Work on your Paper LAST DAY TO WITHDRAW FROM CLASS IS APRIL 22</p>
Week 14	Apr. 25	<p>Class does not meet; professor available in extra office hours Work on your Paper DUE TUESDAY NIGHT: Second Draft of Final Paper</p>

Week 14 (cont.)	Apr. 28	Read drafts for Fellow Students DUE: Comments on Peer Drafts Class Discussion of Drafts
Week 15	May 2	The 1990s: Security, Surveillance, Giuliani, and 9/11 <i>Empire City</i> pp. 891-976 and <i>America's Urban</i> , Chapter 11 (first section).
	May 5	New York Since 9/11: Bloomberg, Occupy, Sandy, and De Blasio <i>America's Urban</i> , Chapter 11 (finish); Michael Bloomberg, "Shaping New York City's Future After Hurricane Sandy," December 6, 2012, http://www.mikebloomberg.com/news/shaping-new-york-citys-future-after-hurricane-sandy/ and Ruth Milkman, Stephanie Luce, and Penny Lewis, <i>Changing the Subject: A bottom-up Account of Occupy Wall Street in New York City</i> (New York: CUNY Murphy Institute, 2013), https://media.sps.cuny.edu/filestore/1/5/7/1_a05051d2117901d/1571_92f562221b8041e.pdf and Matt Flegenheimer, "Ex-Mayor Is Scorned (and Affirmed) at City Hall," <i>New York Times</i> , September 17, 2014, A1 , http://www.nytimes.com/2014/09/17/nyregion/at-city-hall-a-tussle-over-bloombergs-legacy.html
Week 16	May 9	No Class – Friday Classes Meet
Week 17	May 14	FINAL EXAM TIME DUE SUNDAY: Final Research Paper

Grading Rubric for Writing Assignments				
Argument, Content & Development 47%	Poor - Argument is missing or unclear. - Content is incomplete. - Major points are not clear and /or persuasive. - Specific examples are not used. - Suggested questions are not used to structure assignment.	Fair - Content is not comprehensive and /or persuasive. - Major points are addressed, but not well supported. - Responses are inadequate or do not address assignment. - Specific examples do not support arguments and/or are not related to arguments.	Good - Content is accurate. - Argument is persuasive. - Major points are stated. - Responses are adequate and address assignment. - Content and purpose of the writing are clear. - Specific examples are used to support arguments.	Excellent - Content is comprehensive and accurate. - Argument is persuasive. - Major points are stated clearly and are well supported. - Responses are excellent, addressing the assignment and larger course concepts. - Content and purpose of the writing are clear. - Specific examples are used to support arguments.
Organization & Structure 20%	Poor - Organization and structure detract from the message of the writer. - Paragraphs are disjointed and lack transition of thoughts.	Fair - Structure of the paper is not easy to follow. - Paragraph transitions are awkward and need improvement. - Conclusion is missing, or if provided, does not flow from the body of the paper.	Good - Structure is mostly clear and easy to follow. - Paragraph transitions work. - Conclusion is logical.	Excellent - Structure of the paper is clear and easy to follow. - Paragraph transitions are logical and maintain the flow of thought throughout the paper. - Conclusion is logical and flows from the body of the paper.
Grammar, Punctuation & Spelling 16%	Poor - Paper contains numerous grammatical, punctuation, and spelling errors. - Language uses jargon or conversational tone.	Fair - Paper contains few grammatical, punctuation and spelling errors. - Language lacks clarity or includes the use of some jargon or conversational tone.	Good - Rules of grammar, usage, and punctuation are followed with minor errors. - Spelling is correct.	Excellent - Rules of grammar, usage, and punctuation are followed; spelling is correct. - Language is clear and precise; sentences display consistently strong, varied structure.
Citations 11%	Poor - Citations are not used at all.	Fair - Citations are used for some but not other instances.	Good - Citations are used for primary sources, but not to other readings.	Excellent - Citations are used for all instances, both to primary source and other readings as needed.
Format 6%	Poor - Paper lacks many elements of correct formatting. - Paper is inadequate/excessive in length.	Fair - Paper follows most guidelines. - Paper is over/ under word length.	Good - Paper follows designated guidelines. - Paper is the appropriate length as described for the assignment. - Format is good.	Excellent - Paper follows all designated guidelines. - Paper is the appropriate length as described for the assignment. - Format enhances readability of paper.